

OPEN ACCESS

EDITED BY

Anand Mohan,
University of Georgia, United States

REVIEWED BY

Shima Saffarionpour,
University of Toronto, Canada
Clemens Kilian Weiss,
Bingen Technical University of Applied
Sciences, Germany

*CORRESPONDENCE

Federica Turrini,
✉ federica.turrini@unige.it

¹PRESENT ADDRESS

Valentina Orlandi,
AIMPLAS, Valencia, Spain

RECEIVED 23 February 2026

REVISED 02 April 2026

ACCEPTED 03 April 2026

PUBLISHED 24 April 2026

CITATION

Orlandi V, Grasso F, Turrini F, Mangas A,
Agostinis L and Boggia R (2026)
Sustainable valorization of insect
processing by products via enzymatic
assisted extraction of chitin.
Front. Food Sci. Technol. 6:1815905.
doi: 10.3389/frfst.2026.1815905

COPYRIGHT

© 2026 Orlandi, Grasso, Turrini, Mangas,
Agostinis and Boggia. This is an open-
access article distributed under the terms
of the [Creative Commons Attribution
License \(CC BY\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The use, distribution or
reproduction in other forums is permitted,
provided the original author(s) and the
copyright owner(s) are credited and that
the original publication in this journal is
cited, in accordance with accepted
academic practice. No use, distribution or
reproduction is permitted which does not
comply with these terms.

Sustainable valorization of insect processing by products via enzymatic assisted extraction of chitin

Valentina Orlandi^{1†}, Federica Grasso², Federica Turrini^{2,3*},
Ana Mangas¹, Lodovico Agostinis¹ and Raffaella Boggia^{2,4}

¹Department of Pharmacy, University of Genova, Genova, Italy, ²Aimplas, Asociación de Investigación de Materiales Plásticos Y Conexas, Valencia, Spain, ³National Center for the Development of New Technologies in Agriculture (Agritech), Napoli, Italy, ⁴National Biodiversity Future Center (NBFC), Palermo, Italy

Processing residues from adult *Tenebrio molitor* were evaluated as a sustainable source of chitin and chitosan through an optimized enzyme-assisted extraction strategy. Preliminary proximate analysis revealed a high chitin fraction and low mineral content, confirming the suitability of the biomass for biopolymer recovery. The enzymatic deproteinization process was compared with a conventional chemical method to assess purification performance. Process parameters were optimized using a Face-Centered Central Composite Design, investigating the combined influence of pH, enzyme concentration, and extraction time, achieving deproteinization efficiencies ranging from 86.1% to 94.1% approaching those obtained by the chemical reference process. Enzyme-extracted chitin showed low residual lipids (0.9–4.8 g/100 g) and minimal ashes (0–0.5 g/100 g), and approximately 7% moisture. ATR-FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of characteristic chitin functional groups; while SEM analysis revealed porous microfibrillar morphology consistent with effective protein removal and structural integrity. Chemical deacetylation of the extracted chitin yielded chitosan with a degree of deacetylation of 85%, and FTIR spectrum overlapped with that of a commercial reference, indicating comparable structural features. TGA displayed a typical multi-stage degradation pattern, including initial moisture loss, major polymer decomposition above 230 °C, and a low residual ash fraction (~2%). Furthermore, the recovered chitosan exhibited a water-binding capacity of 773% ± 19 and a fat-binding capacity of 715% ± 12. Overall, the DoE-optimized enzymatic process enables efficient valorization of insect processing side streams, producing refined chitin and chitosan while supporting environmentally sustainable and circular biorefinery strategies.

KEYWORDS

chitin, chitosan, design of experiment, enzymatic-extraction, insect, side-streams, *Tenebrio molitor*, upcycling

1 Introduction

Chitin is one of the most abundant polysaccharides in nature and represents a key renewable resource for biopolymer production, second only to cellulose in terms of global availability. It is widely distributed across diverse biological matrices, including crustacean shells, fungal cell walls, mollusks, and insect exoskeletons. To date, crustacean waste from the seafood industry remains the primary industrial feedstock for chitin extraction.

However, increasing attention is being directed toward alternative, non-marine sources due to seasonal availability, allergenicity concerns, and the high mineral content of crustacean shells, which necessitates intensive chemical processing. In this context, insect-derived biomass is emerging as a promising and more sustainable source of chitin for industrial applications (Izadi et al., 2025; Karthick Rajan et al., 2024; Kozma et al., 2024; Zarzosa and Kobayashi, 2025).

Among these, insects offer several advantages over conventional crustacean sources for chitin production. Their high reproductive rates, short life cycles, and independence from seasonal constraints enable continuous and scalable biomass supply (Gul et al., 2025). Furthermore, insects can serve as efficient bio converters of low-value organic substrates into high-protein biomass, contributing to waste valorization and resource efficiency. From a processing perspective, insect exoskeletons generally contain lower mineral fractions than crustacean shells, reducing the need for aggressive demineralization treatments and consequently decreasing chemical consumption (Zainol Abidin et al., 2020). These features make insects particularly attractive as an alternative and more sustainable feedstock for chitin and chitosan production (Hahn et al., 2020).

Tenebrio molitor L. (TM), commonly known as the yellow mealworm, is utilized in food and feed applications, thereby fostering the development of industrial-scale rearing systems. According to Errico et al., TM production requires significantly less land and water and results in lower green-house gas and ammonia emissions compared to conventional livestock such as poultry, pigs, sheep, cattle, and aquaculture (Errico et al., 2022). The species' high feed conversion efficiency, rapid growth, and prolific reproduction further enhance its appeal as a sustainable protein source.

The life cycle of TM (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) comprises four stages: egg, larva, pupa, and adult (Frooninckx et al., 2022). Females lay approximately between 250 and 500 eggs, which hatch into larvae that undergo multiple molts (Ribeiro et al., 2018). The duration of each stage is influenced by environmental factors such as temperature and humidity. During the pupal and adult stages, the insect develops a chitin-rich cuticle that becomes increasingly rigid and pigmented, offering enhanced mechanical protection compared to the more flexible larval cuticle (Mohan Kumar and Kungumapriya, 2025). While larvae are favored for their high protein and low chitin content, traits that enhance protein digestibility and bioavailability, the adult stage, despite its high protein content, contains significantly more chitin. This makes adult insects less suitable for nutritional purposes and positions them as a valuable side-stream in insect farming.

Valorizing adult insect side-streams through the extraction of chitin and its derivative chitosan aligns with the principles of the circular economy, enabling the conversion of low-value by-products into high-added-value biopolymers. This upcycling strategy enhances resource efficiency by closing material loops within insect farming systems and reducing waste generation. In this context, adult *T. molitor* residues represent a promising feedstock for integrated biorefinery schemes, where biopolymer recovery can be coupled with the valorization of hydrolyzed protein fractions, thereby maximizing the overall value of the biomass.

Importantly, despite the rapidly expanding interest in insect-derived biopolymers, the systematic valorization of whole adult insects as a dedicated chitin-rich side-stream remains largely unexplored.

In addition, the combination of Enzymatic-Assisted Extraction (EAE) with statistical optimization establishes a more sustainable, food-grade alternative to conventional chemical processing. This approach aims to generate chitin and chitosan with physicochemical properties suitable for applications in the food industry, including active packaging, edible coatings, natural preservatives, and functional ingredients for texture and moisture management, thereby addressing the growing demand for biodegradable and non-toxic materials in sustainable food technology.

Chitin is a linear β 1,4 linked N acetyl D glucosamine polysaccharide that occurs in several crystalline polymorphs, with α chitin being the most common due to its high crystallinity and extensive hydrogen bonding. (Kozma et al., 2022; Terkula Iber et al., 2022). These structural features provide mechanical strength and low solubility, defining chitin's role in invertebrate exoskeletons and fungal cell walls while also complicating its extraction and processing (Hahn et al., 2020; Kozma et al., 2022). Through deacetylation (a process involving the alkaline hydrolysis of acetamido groups), chitin can be converted into chitosan, a more versatile polysaccharide. The resulting increase in free primary amine groups and reduction in molecular weight enhance chitosan's solubility in mildly acidic solutions (Feng et al., 2012). A degree of acetylation (DA) threshold of 50% is commonly used to distinguish between chitin and chitosan: biopolymers with DA > 50% are considered chitin and are largely insoluble, while those with DA < 50% are classified as chitosan and are soluble in dilute acids (Cunha et al., 2012; Rinaudo, 2006).

Chitosan is highly valued for its biocompatibility, biodegradability, antimicrobial activity, and low environmental toxicity (H. Kim et al., 2023). Its modifiable functional groups further enhance its utility across diverse sectors, including biomedicine, agriculture, textiles, papermaking, wastewater treatment, and the food industry. Applications range from functional foods and animal feed to insecticides, disinfectants, medical devices (e.g., artificial skin, surgical sutures), and active packaging films designed to extend the shelf life of fresh foods by leveraging chitosan's antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties (Chandarana et al., 2025; Chen et al., 2023; Pighinelli, 2019).

While chemical extraction is still the predominant method in industrial applications due to its fast processing, it relies on harsh acids and alkalis, generating hazardous waste and raising serious environmental concerns. In particular, these processes require large volumes of concentrated reagents and produce highly saline effluents, which significantly increase the environmental footprint of chitin production (Arbia et al., 2013; Hosney et al., 2022; Islam et al., 2023; Mohan et al., 2022). Conversely, biotechnological strategies, such as enzymatic extraction, offer a greener alternative by reducing chemical inputs and minimizing ecological impact, despite their slower processing time.

In this study, chitin and chitosan recovery was investigated by comparing a widely used conventional chemical extraction method (Hahn et al., 2020; Rehman et al., 2023) with an innovative Enzymatic-Assisted Extraction (EAE). It is hypothesized that the

FIGURE 1
Dried adult TM insect by-products.

enzymatic route, when statistically optimized, can approach the purification efficiency of chemical treatment while reducing environmental impact. EAE was systematically optimized using a Design of Experiments (DoE) framework to improve efficiency and process performance. Unlike traditional chemical treatments, which are energy-intensive and compromise sustainability, this approach focuses on valorizing production side-streams from TM farming, introducing the whole adult insect as a novel source of chitin, thus expanding the potential of insect-based biopolymer recovery. By demonstrating that enzymatic extraction can be optimized to deliver high-quality biopolymers with reduced environmental impact, this work provides a scalable framework for future industrial applications, supporting the transition toward greener materials and circular biorefinery models in the food sector. This work represents one of the first attempts to integrate enzymatic extraction with statistical optimization for insect-derived biopolymers, establishing a foundation for more sustainable and efficient upcycling strategies. While several green alternatives have been proposed to mitigate the environmental impact of chemical processes, no standardized protocol currently exists. Therefore, optimizing the extraction process based on the specific characteristics of the raw material remains a critical area of research (Mersmann et al., 2025).

This work includes a full characterization of the starting biomass and recovered biopolymers, from compositional and structural analyses to functional assessments relevant to food applications. In particular, the starting biomass, (adult TM), was characterized through proximate analysis; similarly, the extracted chitin underwent compositional characterization and was further analyzed using Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to assess its structural and morphological

properties. After deacetylation of chitin, the resulting chitosan was then subjected to preliminary chemical characterization using ATR-FTIR spectroscopy analysis, Thermo-Gravimetric Analysis (TGA), and SEM. Moreover, chitosan's water- and fat-binding capacities were tested to assess its potential functionality as a techno-functional ingredient in food formulations, particularly for improving texture, moisture retention, and fat stabilization in processed products.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Samples

Side-streams from the production of edible TM larvae were provided by Mon Scarabat (L'Olleria, Valencia, Spain). These by-products consist of adult TM insects (Figure 1), which are typically discarded during the larval production process.

After a preliminary dehydration step, the adult insects were ground with a blender Grindomix GM200, Retsch (Haan, Germany) and sieved using a stainless-steel sieve with a 100 μm aperture, resulting in a homogeneous powder free of visible impurities. The processed material was then vacuum-sealed and stored in dark conditions until further use for chitin extraction.

2.2 Chemicals

Ultrapure Milli-Q water (18 M Ω) has been produced by a Millipore Milli-Q system (Bedford, MA, United States of America) and used throughout. All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade. Acetic acid, Alcalase[®], ethyl acetate, sodium hydroxide, hydrogen peroxide 30% were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Company (Steinheim, Germany). Chitosan (50–190 kDa, 75% deacetylated), was obtained from BIOSYNTH (Staad, Switzerland).

2.3 Study design

The study design is illustrated in Figure 2, which outlines the workflow from *T. molitor* adult carcasses through proximate analysis, chitin isolation via chemical and enzymatic treatments, and subsequent characterization of chitin and chitosan.

2.4 Characterization of samples (TM)

The residual moisture content of the samples was determined using the official AOAC method 925.10 while the ash content was measured according to an adapted version of AOAC method 942.05 (AOAC International, 2000), by incinerating the samples at 700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 6 h in a muffle furnace LE 2/11/R7, Nabertherm (Lilienthal, Germany). Protein content was quantified using the Kjeldahl method AOAC 984.13 (AOAC International, 2000), employing an automatic distillation system K-360, Büchi Labortechnik AG, (Flawil, Switzerland). A nitrogen-to-protein conversion factor of 4.76 was applied to calculate the total protein content from the measured crude nitrogen (Costa et al., 2020; Janssen et al., 2017). Lipid content was determined gravimetrically using the Soxhlet extraction method 981.10 (AOAC International, 2000), with ethyl

FIGURE 2
Schematic overview of the present study.

acetate as the extraction solvent (Abutaha and Al-Mekhlafi, 2025). The total carbohydrate content was estimated by subtracting the percentages of total protein, fat, and ash from 100%, assuming that the remaining fraction corresponds primarily to chitin and other carbohydrates. All analyses were performed in triplicate, and results are expressed as mean values \pm standard error.

2.5 Isolation of chitin

A one-step chitin purification protocol was adapted from the method described by Lucas et al. (Jantzen Da Silva Lucas et al., 2021), with slight modifications. Given the low ash and lipid content in TM adult biomass, preliminary demineralization and defatting steps were deemed unnecessary and therefore omitted.

Both chemical and enzymatic deproteinization methods were applied and compared. The chemical extraction served as the reference method (Hahn et al., 2020; Jantzen Da Silva Lucas et al., 2021), while the EAE was investigated as a more sustainable alternative. The EAE conditions were optimized using a DoE approach to maximize chitin recovery while minimizing environmental impact.

The chitin extraction yield (%) was calculated by weighing the insoluble fraction (chitin) obtained after separation from the soluble protein hydrolysates, using the Equation 1 (Luo et al., 2019).

$$\text{Chitin yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{dried isolated chitin (g)}}{\text{dried TM starting biomass (g)}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.5.1 Isolation of chitin by chemical deproteinization

The protein fraction was extracted using 10% sodium hydroxide (10% w/v) for 3 h at 100 °C, according to the method proposed by Al

Hoqani et al. (Said Al Hoqani et al., 2020), with major modifications. During the extraction process, the total soluble solids (TSS) content in the supernatant was monitored every 30 min using a digital refractometer at 20 °C (Hanna Instruments, Italy), and expressed in degrees Brix (°Brix), until a constant value was reached, indicating completion of protein solubilization (Canessa et al., 2025; K.-M. Kim et al., 2010).

2.5.2 Isolation of chitin by enzymatic deproteinization via DoE

The EAE was carried out using Alcalase[®], a commercial endo-protease produced by *Bacillus licheniformis*, following the protocol described by Lucas et al. (Jantzen Da Silva Lucas et al., 2021), with slight modifications. To optimize the enzymatic extraction conditions, a DoE approach was applied. Specifically, a Face-Centered Central Composite Design (FCCCD) was employed, involving three independent variables, i.e., extraction time, pH, and enzyme concentration (expressed as mL of enzyme per Gram of TM biomass), each tested at three levels (−1, 0, 1). The experimental design included a total of 17 runs, comprising three replicates at the central point to assess experimental variability. The chitin extraction yield (%) was selected as the response variable and calculated to evaluate the efficiency of the enzymatic process.

A total of 17 experiments were conducted, according to the formula $2^k + 2k + N$. The experimental matrix and the corresponding design plan (shown in brackets) are presented in Table 1.

Based on the number of factors and their respective levels, the proposed multiple linear regression model, detailed below, consists of 10 coefficients: 1 constant, three linear terms, three interaction terms, and three quadratic terms, respectively (Equation 2).

TABLE 1 Experimental matrix and experimental plan (in brackets), and DoE results: chitin yield (%) and isolation efficiency (%) by EAE vs. chemical process.

Experiment	Time (h)	pH	Enzyme concentration (%)	Yield (%)	Efficiency (%)
1	1(6)	-1 (7)	-1 (0.5)	43.4	90.1
2	1 (6)	1 (10)	-1 (0.5)	41.2	93.6
3	0 (4)	0 (8.5)	-1 (0.5)	43.5	90.0
4	-1 (2)	-1 (7)	-1 (0.5)	45.9	86.1
5	-1 (2)	1 (10)	-1 (0.5)	43.9	89.3
6	1 (6)	0 (8.5)	0 (1)	41.9	92.5
7	0 (4)	-1 (7)	0 (1)	44.1	89.0
8	0 (4)	0 (8.5)	0 (1)	42.0	92.4
9	0 (4)	0 (8.5)	0 (1)	42.1	92.2
10	0 (4)	0 (8.5)	0 (1)	42.2	92.0
11	0 (4)	1 (10)	0 (1)	40.9	94.1
12	-1 (2)	0 (8.5)	0 (1)	43.9	89.3
13	1 (6)	-1 (7)	1 (2)	43.9	89.3
14	1 (6)	1 (10)	1 (2)	40.9	94.1
15	0 (4)	0 (8.5)	1 (2)	42.0	92.4
16	-1 (2)	-1 (7)	1 (2)	44.8	87.9
17	-1 (2)	1 (10)	1 (2)	41.5	93.2

$$y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + b_{12}x_1x_2 + b_{13}x_1x_3 + b_{23}x_2x_3 + b_{11}x_1^2 + b_{22}x_2^2 + b_{33}x_3^2 \quad (2)$$

For each experiment, approximately 10 g of TM adult biomass were suspended in distilled water at a 1:10 w/v ratio. The initial pH of the suspension was measured using a HI5221, Hanna Instruments pHmeter (Villafranca Padovana, Italy) and was approximately 7. When required, the pH was adjusted to the target value specified in the experimental design using a NaOH solution. The selected enzyme was then added, and the enzymatic hydrolysis was carried out at a controlled temperature of 70 °C. After the reaction, the suspension was filtered to separate the solid fraction. The recovered solid, corresponding to isolated chitin, was washed with distilled water until neutral pH was achieved, and subsequently dried at 55 °C until a constant weight was reached.

The efficiency of the enzymatic extraction was evaluated by comparing it to a chemical reference process, which involved treating the biomass with a high-temperature NaOH solution, as reported in the previous paragraph [(Said Al Hoqani et al., 2020)]. This chemical method was considered to have 100% efficiency in removing non-chitinous material. For each of the 17 experimental runs, the amount of non-chitinous material removed during enzymatic extraction was calculated and expressed as a percentage relative to the chemical method (Equation 3 reported below).

$$\text{Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{non chitinous material removed with enzymatic deproteinization (g)}}{\text{non chitinous material removed with chemical deproteinization (g)}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

The elaboration of the experimental data was performed using CAT, the Chemometric Agil Tool, an R-based chemometric software created by the Italian Chemical Society's Chemistry Group (Leardi et al., s.d.).

2.6 Conversion of chitin to chitosan through deacetylation

Chitin deacetylation was performed using a concentrated sodium hydroxide solution for an extended period, as reported in several studies (Kurita, 2006; No and Meyers, 1995; Novikov et al., 2023), specifically, the biomass was treated with 60% NaOH at a solid-to-liquid ratio of 1:10 (w/v) at 100 °C for 24 h. After completion, the suspension was filtered, and the resulting chitosan pellets were thoroughly washed with distilled water until reaching a neutral pH. The chitosan was then dried at 55 °C until a constant weight was achieved. Bleaching of chitosan was performed using 30% H₂O₂ at 90 °C for 30 min, following the method described by Al Hoqani et al. (Said Al Hoqani et al., 2020), with minor modifications. The suspension was subsequently filtered, and the pellets were rinsed with distilled water. Solubility of chitosan 1% (w/v) was determined both before and after bleaching using acetic acid 1% (v/v).

2.7 Proximate analysis

The ash content was determined by ignition at 700 °C for 6 h in a Nabertherm muffle furnace LE 2/11/R7 (Lilienthal, Germany). As for the lipid content, Soxhlet method was performed on isolated chitin samples using ethyl acetate as extraction solvent (Abutaha and Al-Mekhlafi, 2025). The residual moisture was evaluated using a Sartorius thermo-gravimetric humidity analyzer (Massachusetts, United States).

2.8 ATR-FTIR (Attenuated Total Reflectance–Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy)

For chemical identification, the ATR-FTIR spectra were recorded using an FT-IR spectrophotometer Perkin Elmer, Inc., (Waltham, MA, US) from 4,000 to 600 cm^{-1} , with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , collecting 16 scans per sample. The degree of deacetylation (DDA) of chitosan was determined according to the method described by Weißpflog et al. (Weißpflog et al., 2021). The calculation was based on the ratio between the integrated area of the amide I band ($\approx 1,646 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), associated with the $-\text{CO}-\text{NH}$ groups, and the area of the symmetric or asymmetric $-\text{CH}_2$ stretching vibrations ($\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$, $\approx 2,870 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\approx 2,930 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), used as reference bands. The areas of the selected peaks were calculated and the ratio between amide I and $-\text{CH}_2$ stretching bands was used to estimate the DDA, which decreases with increasing deacetylation. As reported in the literature, accurate baseline correction of the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ peak was applied to minimize errors and ensure reliable quantification (Dimzon and Knepper, 2015; Duarte et al., 2002).

2.9 TGA (Thermogravimetric Analysis)

The thermal properties were studied using a thermo-gravimetric analyzer TA Instruments TGA QIR5000, (New Castle, DE, United States) on 2 mg of sample, following the temperature program of first heating cycle from 30 °C to 900 °C at a rate of 20.00 °C/min in air.

2.10 SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy)

Sample morphology was examined using a Hitachi scanning electron microscope TM-1000, (Tokyo, Japan), operated at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV. The instrument was equipped with an energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) detector Oxford Instruments, (Oxford, United Kingdom). For SEM analysis, samples were prepared by placing them onto carbon adhesive tape and the surface of the samples was coated with gold.

2.11 WBC (Water Binding Capacity) and FBC (Fat Binding Capacity)

The water-(WBC) and oil-(FBC) binding capacities of chitosan were assessed following the procedure described by Milinković Budinčić with slight modifications (Milinković Budinčić et al., 2025). A 0.2 g of chitosan was weighed, and 2 mL of either distilled water or vegetable oil was added. The mixture was vortexed for 5 s every 5 min over a 30-min period, then centrifuged at 4,000 rpm for 20 min at 25 °C. The supernatant

was removed, and the binding capacity was calculated using the Equations 4, 5 below.

$$\text{WBC (\%)} = \frac{\text{water bound (g)}}{\text{initial chitosan weight (g)}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{FBC (\%)} = \frac{\text{fat bound (g)}}{\text{initial chitosan weight (g)}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

2.12 Statistical analysis

All the tests were performed in triplicate, and the result is shown as the mean and standard error. The software CAT was used to elaborate experimental data and the DoE (Leardi et al., s.d.).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Characterization of TM side streams

The results of the proximate analysis of TM side streams are reported in Table 2, providing a compositional basis for evaluating their suitability as a feedstock for chitin extraction.

The residual moisture content of TM was approximately 10%, aligning with the upper threshold recommended to inhibit microbial proliferation and thereby extend shelf life (Vera Zambrano et al., 2019).

Available literature provides limited quantitative data on the protein content of adult TM. In chitin-rich matrices, elevated total nitrogen levels may artificially inflate protein estimates when conventional nitrogen-to-protein conversion factors are applied. In the present study, the protein content was estimated at approximately 50%, consistent with previously reported values (Kim, Seong Hyeon et al., 2012; Muñoz-Seijas et al., 2025). Protein estimation was based on a conversion factor of 4.76, as proposed by Janssen (Janssen et al., 2017), which accounts for the specific amino acid profile of insect proteins. This factor is notably lower than the conventional 6.25, which, although still commonly used, may lead to an overestimation of protein content by up to 17%, as reported by Boulos et al. (Boulos et al., 2020).

Several authors highlighted that the ash content in insects is significantly lower than in crustaceans, which are traditionally used as the primary source for chitin extraction (Khatami et al., 2024; Zainol Abidin et al., 2020). In the biomass analyzed, the ash content was found to be below 4%, suggesting that a demineralization step may not be necessary for subsequent chitin purification.

The lipid content of TM biomass was approximately 5%, as determined via Soxhlet extraction using ethyl acetate, a green solvent chosen in alignment with the second principle of green chemistry (Chemat et al., 2012), and according to the findings by Abutaha et al. (Abutaha and Al-Mekhlafi, 2025). In contrast, conventional defatting procedures typically employ petroleum-derived solvents such as hexane (Mei et al., 2024; Son et al., 2021), which pose environmental concerns.

The total carbohydrate content of TM adult carcasses, including structural polysaccharides such as chitin, was estimated to be approximately 31%. This value is consistent with the findings of Sudwischer et al. (Sudwischer et al., 2025), who reported a chitin

TABLE 2 Proximate analysis of TM side streams.

Residual moisture (g/100 g)	10.1 ± 0.2
Proteins (g/100 g)	50.0 ± 1.2
Ashes (g/100 g)	3.9 ± 0.0
Lipids (g/100 g)	4.8 ± 0.2
Total carbohydrates ^a (g/100 g)	31.2

^aTotal carbohydrates were estimated by difference (100% – protein–ashes–lipids), assuming the remainder consists mainly of chitin and other carbohydrates. Results are expressed as mean value ± standard error.

content of similar magnitude in dehydrated adult beetles, suggesting that chitin represents a major fraction of the carbohydrate pool in insect biomass, as confirmed by Son et al. (Son et al., 2021).

3.2 Isolation of chitin through chemical deproteinization process

The chemical isolation process yielded 37.2% chitin, with a residual moisture of 7% and an ash content of 1.9%. Lipid extraction from the chemically isolated chitin was below the detection limit.

3.3 Isolation of chitin through enzymatic deproteinization via DoE

In line with the six principles of green chemistry (Chemat et al., 2012), and with the aim of overcoming the limitations associated with chemical chitin purification, several biotechnological approaches have been developed to recover high-quality chitin (Shetranjiwalla and Ononiwu, 2025). Among the reported advantages of these methods are cost-effectiveness and improved safety, although their application remains confined to laboratory scale (Verardi et al., 2023). Enzymatic treatment is currently considered a promising alternative (Mathew et al., 2021). However, despite its benefits, enzymatic deproteinization presents some drawbacks: in addition to the higher cost of enzymes, elevated protein content in the biomass can result in reaction times comparable to or even longer than those required by chemical methods (Zainol Abidin et al., 2020). In general, enzymatic methods allow for milder reaction conditions (commonly 25 °C–59 °C), enabling protein removal with minimal deacetylation and reduced damage to the chitin polymer chain. Nevertheless, deproteinization efficiency rarely exceeds 90%, even with prolonged reaction times, due to enzyme activity loss and depletion of binding sites. Residual protein content in enzymatically isolated chitin is typically between 5% and 10%, making this method less efficient than chemical deproteinization (Younes and Rinaudo, 2015). Among the available enzymes, Alcalase[®] was selected due to its well-documented efficiency as a proteolytic agent in the deproteinization step of chitin extraction. Alcalase[®] is a commercial serine endopeptidase characterized by broad substrate specificity and high activity under relatively mild pH and temperature conditions. In the extraction of chitin from insect biomass such as *T. molitor*, the main challenge is the removal of proteins tightly associated with the chitin matrix. Alcalase[®] is particularly effective in this context, as it hydrolyzes a wide range of peptide bonds, leading to a high degree of protein removal while preserving the structural integrity of chitin. Its selection is further supported by previous studies on TM, where Alcalase[®] demonstrated superior proteolytic performance

FIGURE 3
Coefficients plot.

compared to other commercial enzymes. In particular, Kim et al. demonstrated that Alcalase[®] achieves a higher degree of protein hydrolysis at all tested reaction times on TM larvae compared to other commercial enzymes, resulting in more effective removal of proteins from the chitin matrix (H. Kim et al., 2023). Additional studies confirm that Alcalase[®] exhibits high proteolytic activity toward insect proteins, supporting its suitability for chitin extraction processes (Gonzalez-de La Rosa et al., 2024). Moreover, Alcalase[®] is also widely used in industrial bioprocesses, supporting its potential scalability. Alkaline proteases are extensively used in industrial sectors such as food processing, detergents, and waste management, highlighting the robustness and scalability of Alcalase[®]-based processes (Sharma et al., 2017).

The results of the DoE are presented in Table 1 as chitin yield (%), ranging from about 41% to 46% with the highest of 40.9% obtained in experiments n. 11 and 14. However, in the context of chitin isolation, extraction yield alone is not considered the primary criterion for evaluating process efficiency (Saravana et al., 2018). On the contrary, minimizing the yield may be desirable, as higher values can indicate the presence of residual impurities such as proteins, lipids, or ash, compromising the purity of the final product. In line with this, the slight decrease in yield observed at higher pH values and longer extraction times can be attributed to the more effective removal of these non-chitin components. Under these conditions, the enzymatic action promotes deeper degradation and solubilization of residual proteins and other impurities, resulting in a lower mass of the recovered solid fraction. Consequently, the reduction in apparent yield reflects an improvement in purification efficiency rather than a loss of chitin, which is consistent with the corresponding increase in isolation efficiency reported in Table 1.

With regard to the relatively narrow differences observed in both chitin yield and isolation efficiency between chemical and

FIGURE 4
Response surfaces (pH vs. extraction time) on yield are shown for three enzyme concentrations: 0.5% (level -1) in panel (a), 1% (level 0) in panel (b), and 2% (level 1) in panel (c).

enzymatic treatments, it is important to emphasize that the omission of preliminary defatting and demineralization steps was a deliberate methodological choice consistently applied to both extraction routes. This strategy ensured a fair and coherent comparison under identical pre-treatment conditions. The adult TM biomass used in this study exhibited low lipid (~5%) and ash (<4%) contents, values at the lower end of those reported for insect-derived raw materials. Under these conditions, residual lipids and minerals are unlikely to significantly hinder either extraction route, and any residual effect is expected to influence both processes in a

comparable manner, without introducing systematic bias. While the absence of defatting and demineralization may contribute to a certain degree of background variability, potentially limiting the magnitude of the differences observed across DoE conditions, this trade-off was intentionally accepted to prioritize process simplification, scalability, and sustainability. Similar reduced-step extraction strategies have been reported for TM and other low-ash, low-lipid insect biomasses, highlighting the economic and environmental advantages of avoiding solvent-based and acid-based pre-treatments (Jantzen Da Silva Lucas et al., 2021).

TABLE 3 Characterization of isolated chitin via EAE.

Experiment	Yield (%)	Lipids (%)	Ashes (%)
1	43.4	3.9	0.1
2	41.2	1.1	0.5
3	43.5	1.3	0.2
4	45.9	4.8	0.5
5	43.9	2.0	0.4
6	41.9	2.8	0.2
7	44.1	3.1	0.5
8	42.0	2.6	0.5
9	42.1	2.7	0.1
10	42.2	2.7	0.1
11	40.9	1.9	0.5
12	43.9	2.3	0.1
13	43.9	3.9	0.2
14	40.9	0.9	0.3
15	42.0	2.6	0.3
16	44.8	4.7	0.1
17	41.5	1.2	0.1

Consequently, within this experimental framework, the comparison between chemical and enzymatic extraction remains valid, as the observed differences primarily reflect the intrinsic mechanisms of the two approaches rather than differences in biomass pre-treatment.

The model of the design is reported below (Equation 6).

$$y = 42.27^{***} - 0.87x_1^{***} - 1.37x_2^{***} - 0.48x_3^{**} + 0.01x_1x_2 + 0.46x_1x_3^{**} - 0.26x_2x_3^{*} + 0.50x_1^2^{*} + 0.10x_2^2 + 0.35x_3^2 \quad (6)$$

Stars represent the statistical significance (p-value; * = 0.05, ** = 0.01, *** = 0.001), the standard deviation of the residuals (8 d.o.f.) is 0.3, and the experimental standard deviation (7 d.o.f.) is 2.1, with an explained variance of 95.96%.

The coefficients plot is reported below (Figure 3).

The statistical significance of the coefficients reported in Figure 3 underscores the relevance of pH and extraction time as the primary variables governing the chitin isolation process. Within the investigated range, higher pH levels and longer extraction times were associated with lower yields, corresponding to enhanced isolation purity.

In contrast, enzyme concentration exhibited a comparatively minor main effect, indicating that efficient process performance can be achieved using low enzyme loadings, with the additional benefit of reducing enzyme-related costs (Cahyaningtyas et al., 2022). Nevertheless, a significant interaction between extraction time and enzyme concentration was observed, highlighting the time-dependent role of enzymatic treatment. At prolonged reaction times, increasing enzyme concentration partially counterbalanced the yield reduction, indicating diminishing returns in terms of purity and

confirming that excessive enzyme loading is not advantageous. This behavior reflects the kinetic limitations of the process: while additional enzyme molecules provide more active sites for protein hydrolysis, the accessibility of tightly bound proteins in the chitin matrix becomes the limiting factor. Consequently, further increases in enzyme loading result in diminishing returns regarding both yield and purity, confirming that excessive enzyme application is not advantageous from both a technical and economic standpoint (Berton et al., 2018).

These statistical insights are further illustrated by the response surface plots (Figure 4), which visually depict how yield decreases with increasing pH and extraction time, indicating enhanced purity, with enzyme concentration exerting a moderate influence. The observed decrease in yield at higher pH values and prolonged extraction times is attributed to the combined effects of polymer degradation and partial solubilization of chitin. Elevated pH can induce mild deacetylation, weakening the chitin structure, while extended reaction times increase exposure to alkaline or enzymatic conditions, promoting chain cleavage and mechanical losses during handling. Consequently, although higher pH and longer extraction times may improve protein removal and purity, they lead to a reduction in the overall recovered chitin yield (Mathew et al., 2021).

Since chemical deproteinization yielded the most satisfactory results in one-step isolation, the efficiency of the enzymatic method was evaluated in comparison with the chemical protocol. The removal of non-chitinous material by EAE was therefore quantified as a percentage relative to the amount removed by the chemical method, which was used as the reference. The corresponding results are reported in Table 1.

The purification efficiency of the enzymatic process, expressed as efficiency (%), ranged from 86.1% to 94.1% compared to chemical isolation. A difference of less than 10% in isolation efficiency was observed between the mildest conditions tested (86.1%) and the most efficient enzymatic treatment (94.1%). Previous studies (Hisham et al., 2024; Younes and Rinaudo, 2015; Zainol Abidin et al., 2020) have reported that enzymatic activity is most effective within the first 1 to 2 h of extraction, and the results obtained in this study are consistent with those findings.

While the DoE was designed to model the system within a practical extraction time window (up to 6 h), additional experiments were performed at prolonged extraction times to evaluate the robustness of the observed trends and to determine whether further improvements could be achieved beyond the optimized conditions. However, prolonged treatments (24 h) produced higher yields, indicating reduced purification efficiency. This decline could be attributed to progressive enzyme deactivation and the exhaustion of available binding sites over long reaction periods. Overall, the findings confirm that enzymatic extraction becomes less effective when reaction times exceed the optimal window. These results reinforce the time-dependent nature of the process identified through the DoE.

3.4 Characterization of chitin

3.4.1 Proximate analysis of chitin

The detailed characterization of each enzymatically isolated chitin sample is presented in Table 3.

The chitin obtained through EAE exhibited a residual lipid content ranging from 1% to 5%, indicating that enzymatically isolated chitin is less purified from lipids compared to the chemically isolated counterpart, which showed no detectable lipid residues. Regarding ash content, the values obtained ranged from approximately 0%–0.5%, which is comparable to those found by Kherbache et al. in chitin obtained from shrimp shells waste (Kherbache et al., 2022) and lower than the levels observed in chemically isolated chitin. The residual moisture content of all chitin samples was consistently around 7%.

3.4.2 ATR-FTIR (Attenuated Total Reflectance–Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy) of chitin

The FTIR spectra of chitin isolated through both chemical and enzymatic processes are shown in Figure 5. For the enzymatic

extraction, three representative spectra are included: one obtained under the mildest experimental conditions (Mild_Exp.4, in yellow), one under intermediate conditions (Intermediate_Exp.8, in orange), and one under the strongest conditions (Strong_Exp.14, in red), as defined by the DoE. Additionally, the spectrum of chitin isolated via chemical extraction is also reported (Chemical, in green).

The ATR-FTIR profile of chitin isolated from TM closely resembles spectra previously reported in the literature (Azzi et al., 2024; Chalhaf et al., 2023; H. Kim et al., 2023). In the region between 3,000 and 3,600 cm^{-1} , the broad band corresponds to O–H stretching vibrations typical of polysaccharides (Gieroba et al., 2023). A peak around 3,000 cm^{-1} is observed, corresponding to the C–H stretching vibration of the cis-double bond (=CH) (Alshuaiel and Al-Ghouti, 2020). Additionally, peaks near 2,920 cm^{-1} and 2,850 cm^{-1} are associated with symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations of aliphatic– CH_2 groups (Ciumac et al., 2017), indicative of lipid content. The Amide I band, located between 1,660 and 1,620 cm^{-1} (Hasan et al., 2022), and the Amide II band around 1,550 cm^{-1} , are clearly visible in the chitin spectra, and corresponds to vibrations of the NHCOCH_3 group (Jantzen Da Silva Lucas et al., 2021). Aromatic skeletal vibrations coupled with C–H in-plane bending and C–O stretching appeared at 1,370–1,300 cm^{-1} , while the band around 1,250–1,260 cm^{-1} is attributed to O–H bending vibrations (Shin et al., 2019).

3.4.3 SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) of chitin

The morphology of chitin isolated via chemical and enzymatic processes was examined using SEM and compared with the starting TM biomass (Figure 6).

Alongside the chemically extracted chitin, shown in Figure 7a, for comparison representative samples of chitin isolated via enzymatic extraction were selected based on the DoE: the least purified sample (mildest conditions, Exp. n. 4, Figure 7b), the moderately purified sample (intermediate conditions, Exp. n. 8,

FIGURE 6
SEM images of adult TM at 270x and 540x.

FIGURE 7
SEM images of chitin: (a) chitin isolated via chemical extraction; (b) chitin isolated via enzymatic extraction (mildest conditions of DoE); (c) chitin isolated via enzymatic extraction (intermediate conditions of DoE); (d) chitin isolated via enzymatic extraction (strongest conditions of DoE).

Figure 7c), and the most purified sample (strongest conditions, Figure 7d).

The complex texture of the starting TM biomass is markedly different from the structure observed in any of the isolated chitin samples, suggesting the effectiveness of both extraction processes. No significant morphological differences are observed between chitin isolated via chemical and enzymatic methods in the SEM micrographs. All chitin samples exhibit a rough surface, characterized by the presence of pores and microfibrillar structures.

3.5 Deacetylation of chitin to obtain chitosan

Starting from the selected chitin via DoE, i.e., condition Exp n. 14 (6 h, pH = 10, 2% enzyme), chitosan is obtained through the deacetylation of chitin, a process involving the hydrolysis of acetamide groups (Pellis et al., 2022). Due to its cost-effectiveness and practicality, chemical deacetylation is commonly employed at an industrial scale (Shetranjiwalla and Ononiwu, 2025). However, the harsh conditions of this process can also break glycosidic bonds within the polymer, resulting in a reduction of molecular weight (Novikov et al., 2023), which can influence both the technological properties and the bioactivity (Gómez-Mascaraque et al., 2016). The final product is a copolymer composed of N-acetylglucosamine and D-glucosamine units; the proportion of N-acetylglucosamine units in the chain is expressed as the DDA (Czechowska-Biskup et al., 2018).

The solubility of the extracted chitosan was assessed by dissolving the material at 1% (w/v) in a 0.5% (v/v) acetic acid solution, both before and after the bleaching step. In all cases, the samples exhibited complete solubility under these conditions.

3.6 Characterization of chitosan

3.6.1 ATR-FTIR (Attenuated Total Reflectance–Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy) of chitosan

The spectra of commercial and extracted chitosan (Figure 8) exhibited similar profiles, confirming the structural consistency between the two samples. Both materials displayed characteristic absorption bands of chitosan: Amide A and Amide B appeared in the regions of 3,000–3,600 cm^{-1} and around 2,900 cm^{-1} , respectively; Amide I was observed near 1,650 cm^{-1} , while Amide II and Amide III were detected at approximately 1,550 cm^{-1} and 1,300 cm^{-1} , respectively. The spectral region between 1,500 and 1,700 cm^{-1} is widely recognized as a key indicator for distinguishing chitosan from chitin. In particular, the Amide I band is typical of chitin, whereas its attenuation in chitosan reflects the removal of acetyl groups during deacetylation (Ghanem et al., 2025). The ATR-FTIR spectrum of the extracted chitosan closely matches that of the commercial sample, supporting the successful conversion of chitin into chitosan.

The DDA was assessed for both samples, yielding values of 75% for commercial chitosan and 85% for the extracted material, thereby demonstrating the high efficiency of the applied deacetylation process.

3.6.2 SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) of chitosan

SEM was employed to investigate the surface morphology of both commercial and extracted chitosan samples. Commercial chitosan exhibited a relatively homogeneous structure when observed at magnifications of 320 \times and 270 \times (Figure 9a), whereas the chitosan obtained through the extraction process displayed a comparable morphology at $\times 300$ magnification (Figure 9b). The similarity between the two samples suggests that

the extraction protocol successfully produced chitosan with structural characteristics analogous to those of the commercial material.

A comparison with the original chitin structure (Figure 7) highlights significant morphological changes resulting from the deacetylation process. Chitin typically presents a well-organized

architecture with distinct pores, indicative of its crystalline nature. These features were absent from the chitosan samples, which appeared as irregular aggregates lacking a defined pattern. Such structural alterations confirm the removal of acetyl groups and the disruption of the ordered crystalline domains, thereby validating the efficiency of the deacetylation step. This transformation is consistent with previous reports describing the conversion of chitin into chitosan, where the loss of acetyl functionalities leads to a more amorphous and less porous morphology.

3.6.3 TGA (Thermogravimetric Analysis) of chitosan

TGA revealed a multi-stage degradation pattern, as evident from the derivative weight-loss curve (Figure 10), which shows the same trend reported by Min et al. (Min et al., 2004).

The initial mass reduction below 100 °C is attributed to the evaporation of residual moisture and loosely bound water (Zawadzki and Kaczmarek, 2010). The second stage, occurring between approximately 230 °C and 400 °C, corresponds to the thermal decomposition of the chitosan polymer backbone, resulting in a significant mass loss (Pereira et al., 2013). Beyond 600 °C, the weight stabilizes, indicating the presence of a thermally

FIGURE 9
SEM images of chitosan: (a) commercial chitosan; (b) extracted chitosan.

FIGURE 10
TGA of extracted chitosan.

stable inorganic residue (ash content). This final residual mass plateau, accounting for approximately 2% of the original sample mass, reflects the non-volatile components remaining after complete thermal degradation.

The temperature of moisture release, together with the onset and extent of polymer backbone degradation and the amount of thermally stable inorganic residue, collectively define the material's thermal stability and purity. These parameters are critical for determining appropriate processing conditions (e.g., film formation, thermal activation, or sterilization) and for evaluating the suitability of chitosan for technologically demanding applications such as biomedicine, packaging, and advanced materials.

3.6.4 WBC (Water Binding Capacity) and FBC (Fat Binding Capacity) of chitosan

The WBC, intended as the ability of water to associate with hydrophilic substances, and FBC, i.e., the amount of oil absorbed per unit weight of chitosan, were measured, yielding values of $773\% \pm 19\%$ and $715\% \pm 12\%$, respectively, higher than the results reported by Nafary et al. (WBC = 632–609% and FBC = 419–386%) for chitosan obtained from *Tenebrio Molitor* Beetles (Nafary et al., 2023). The simultaneous presence of high WBC and FBC suggests a well-balanced chitosan structure capable of efficiently interacting with both hydrophilic and lipophilic compounds, likely related to an appropriate DDA and favorable polymer morphology. Overall, these results confirm the suitability of the obtained chitosan for applications in the food, packaging, and biomedical fields, where effective moisture and lipid retention are required.

4 Conclusion

Global production of edible insects is expected to continue rising due to their environmental sustainability and nutritional value. Adopting eco-friendly strategies such as enzyme-assisted extraction (EAE) for managing insect-farming by-products can further enhance the sustainability of this expanding sector.

In this content, this study presents a green and effective approach for recovering chitin and chitosan from *T. molitor* adult side-streams. Although EAE remains less efficient than conventional chemical methods, it offers clear advantages in terms of reduced environmental impact and the possibility of

valorizing additional biomass fractions, such as hydrolyzed proteins. By integrating EAE with DoE-based optimization, the process achieves high product quality and reproducibility while minimizing resource consumption in terms of chemical demands. In particular, the yield slightly decreased under the conditions of pH 10, 4 h, and 1%–2% enzyme. However, these treatments resulted in the lowest residual lipid and ash contents, indicating a more effective removal of non-chitin components. Consequently, the highest isolation efficiency (94.1%) was obtained despite the slightly lower apparent yield.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that statistically optimized EAE represents a viable and more sustainable alternative for insect-derived biopolymer recovery, enabling the fine tuning of enzymatic conditions (including pH, time, and enzyme concentration), while avoiding unnecessary costs and energy consumption.

This work contributes to advancing circular economy practices within insect production systems and provides a solid foundation for future developments aimed at industrial scalability, cost-effectiveness, and alignment with food safety and regulatory requirements.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/supplementary material, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Author contributions

VO: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft. FG: Data curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft. FT: Data curation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. AM: Formal Analysis, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – review and editing. LA: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review and editing. RB: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review and editing.

Funding

The author(s) declared that financial support was received for this work and/or its publication. This research was funded by the EcoeFISHent project (“Demonstrable and replicable cluster implementing systemic solutions through multilevel circular value chains for eco-efficient valorization of fishing and fish industries side-streams”) belonging to Horizon 2020 Program—Green Deal (Innovation Action, Grant agreement ID: 101036428).

Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Generative AI statement

The author(s) declared that generative AI was used in the creation of this manuscript. During the preparation of this manuscript, the authors used Microsoft Copilot (version GPT-5), Microsoft Corporation, 2026 for the purposes of helping to generate the figure representing the design of this work (Figure 2). The authors have reviewed and edited the output and take full responsibility for the content of this publication.

References

- Abutaha, N., and Al-Mekhlafi, F. A. (2025). Green solvent-based extraction of lipids and proteins from tenebrio molitor: a sustainable approach and cytotoxic activity. *Food Sci. Animal Resour.* 45 (3), 807–820. doi:10.5851/kosfa.2024.e62
- Alshuaib, S. M., and Al-Ghouti, M. A. (2020). Multivariate analysis for FTIR in understanding treatment of used cooking oil using activated carbon prepared from olive stone. *PLoS One* 15 (5), e0232997. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0232997
- AOAC International (2000). *Official methods of analysis of AOAC International*. 17th ed. AOAC International.
- Arbia, W., Adour, L., Amrane, A., and Lounici, H. (2013). Optimization of medium composition for enhanced chitin extraction from *Parapenaeus longirostris* by *Lactobacillus helveticus* using response surface methodology. *Food Hydrocoll.* 31 (2), 392–403. doi:10.1016/j.foodhyd.2012.10.025
- Azzi, M., Elkadaoui, S., Zim, J., Desbrières, J., El Hachimi, Y., and Tolaimate, A. (2024). Tenebrio Molitor breeding rejects as a high source of pure chitin and chitosan: role of the processes, influence of the life cycle stages and comparison with *Hermetia illucens*. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 277, 134475. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.134475
- Berton, P., Shamshina, J. L., Ostadjoo, S., King, C. A., and Rogers, R. D. (2018). Enzymatic hydrolysis of ionic liquid-extracted chitin. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 199, 228–235. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2018.07.014
- Boulos, S., Tännler, A., and Nyström, L. (2020). Nitrogen-to-Protein conversion factors for edible insects on the Swiss market: *T. molitor*, *A. domesticus*, and *L. migratoria*. *Front. Nutr.* 7, 89. doi:10.3389/frnut.2020.00089
- Cahyaningtyas, H. A. A., Suyotha, W., Cheirsilp, B., Prihanto, A. A., Yano, S., and Wakayama, M. (2022). Optimization of protease production by *Bacillus cereus* HMRSC30 for simultaneous extraction of chitin from shrimp shell with value-added recovered products. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 29 (15), 22163–22178. doi:10.1007/s11356-021-17279-8
- Canessa, M., Bo, M., Boggia, R., Calcagnile, L., D'Elia, M., Orlandi, V., et al. (2025). Growth and skeletal structure of the parasitic zoantharian *Savalia savaglia* (Bertoloni, 1819). *Sci. Rep.* 15 (1), 34439. doi:10.1038/s41598-025-17541-w
- Chalghaf, M., Charradi, K., Ksouri, R., Alsulami, Q. A., Jaouani, A., Keshk, S. M. A. S., et al. (2023). Physicochemical characterization of chitin extracted by different treatment sequences from an edible insect. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 253, 127156. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.127156
- Chandarana, C., Bonde, S., Sonwane, S., and Prajapati, B. (2025). Chitosan-based packaging: leading sustainable advancements in the food industry. *Polym. Bull.* 82 (11), 5431–5462. doi:10.1007/s00289-025-05775-7
- Chemat, F., Vian, M. A., and Cravotto, G. (2012). Green extraction of natural products: concept and principles. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 13 (7), 8615–8627. doi:10.3390/ijms13078615
- Chen, Y., Liu, Y., Dong, Q., Xu, C., Deng, S., Kang, Y., et al. (2023). Application of functionalized chitosan in food: a review. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 235, 123716. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.123716
- Ciumac, D., Campbell, R. A., Clifton, L. A., Xu, H., Fragneto, G., and Lu, J. R. (2017). Influence of acyl chain saturation on the membrane-binding activity of a short antimicrobial peptide. *ACS Omega* 2 (11), 7482–7492. doi:10.1021/acsomega.7b01270
- Costa, S., Pedro, S., Lourenço, H., Batista, I., Teixeira, B., Bandarra, N. M., et al. (2020). Evaluation of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae as an alternative food source. *NFS J.* 21, 57–64. doi:10.1016/j.nfs.2020.10.001
- Cunha, R. A., Soares, T. A., Rusu, V. H., Pontes, F. J. S., Franca, E. F., and Lins, R. D. (2012). "The molecular structure and conformational dynamics of chitosan polymers: an integrated perspective from experiments and computational simulations," in *The complex world of polysaccharides*. Editor D. N. Karunaratne (InTech). A. c. Di. doi:10.5772/51803
- Czechowska-Biskup, R., Wach, R. A., Rosiak, J. M., and Ulański, P. (2018). Procedure for determination of the molecular weight of chitosan by viscometry. *Prog. Chem. Appl. Chitin its Deriv.* XXIII, 45–54. doi:10.15259/PCACD.23.004
- Dimzon, I. K. D., and Knepper, T. P. (2015). Degree of deacetylation of chitosan by infrared spectroscopy and partial least squares. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 72, 939–945. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2014.09.050
- Duarte, M. L., Ferreira, M. C., Marvão, M. R., and Rocha, J. (2002). An optimised method to determine the degree of acetylation of chitin and chitosan by FTIR spectroscopy. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 31 (1–3), 1–8. doi:10.1016/S0141-8130(02)00039-9
- Errico, S., Spagnoletta, A., Verardi, A., Moliterni, S., Dimatteo, S., and Sangiorgio, P. (2022). *Tenebrio molitor* as a source of interesting natural compounds, their recovery processes, biological effects, and safety aspects. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 21 (1), 148–197. doi:10.1111/1541-4337.12863
- Feng, F., Liu, Y., Zhao, B., and Hu, K. (2012). Characterization of half N-acetylated chitosan powders and films. *Procedia Eng.* 27, 718–732. doi:10.1016/j.proeng.2011.12.511
- Frooninckx, L., Berrens, S., Van Peer, M., Wuyts, A., Broeckx, L., and Van Miert, S. (2022). Determining the effect of different reproduction factors on the yield and hatching of *Tenebrio molitor* eggs. *Insects* 13 (7), 615. doi:10.3390/insects13070615
- Ghanem, S. N., Marzouk, M. I., Tawfik, M. E., and Eskander, S. B. (2025). Spectroscopic approaches for structural analysis of extracted chitosan generated from chitin deacetylated for escalated periods. *BMC Chem.* 19 (1), 214. doi:10.1186/s13065-025-01558-3
- Gieroba, B., Kalisz, G., Krysa, M., Khalavka, M., and Przekora, A. (2023). Application of vibrational spectroscopic techniques in the study of the natural polysaccharides and their cross-linking process. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24 (3), 2630. doi:10.3390/ijms24032630
- Gómez-Masaraque, L. G., Sanchez, G., and López-Rubio, A. (2016). Impact of molecular weight on the formation of electrosprayed chitosan microcapsules as delivery vehicles for bioactive compounds. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 150, 121–130. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2016.05.012
- Gonzalez-de La Rosa, T., Montserrat-de La Paz, S., and Rivero-Pino, F. (2024). Production, characterisation, and biological properties of *Tenebrio molitor*-derived oligopeptides. *Food Chem.* 450, 139400. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2024.139400
- Gul, T., Khan, N., Latif, R., and Faqir, Y. (2025). A review on the utilization of insect chitosan in the food industry: challenges and opportunities. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 328, 147587. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.147587
- Hahn, T., Tafi, E., Paul, A., Salvia, R., Falabella, P., and Zibek, S. (2020). Current state of chitin purification and chitosan production from insects. *J. Chem. Technol. and Biotechnol.* 95 (11), 2775–2795. doi:10.1002/jctb.6533
- Hasan, S., Boddur, V. M., Viswanath, D. S., and Ghosh, T. K. (2022). *Chitin and chitosan: science and engineering*. Springer International Publishing. doi:10.1007/978-3-031-01229-7

- Hisham, F., Maziati Akmal, M. H., Ahmad, F., Ahmad, K., and Samat, N. (2024). Biopolymer chitosan: potential sources, extraction methods, and emerging applications. *Ain Shams Eng. J.* 15 (2), 102424. doi:10.1016/j.asej.2023.102424
- Hosney, A., Ullah, S., and Barčauskaitė, K. (2022). A review of the chemical extraction of chitosan from shrimp wastes and prediction of factors affecting chitosan yield by using an artificial neural network. *Mar. Drugs* 20 (11), 675. doi:10.3390/md20110675
- Islam, N., Hoque, M., and Taharat, S. F. (2023). Recent advances in extraction of chitin and chitosan. *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 39 (1), 28. doi:10.1007/s11274-022-03468-1
- Izadi, H., Asadi, H., and Bemani, M. (2025). Chitin: a comparison between its main sources. *Front. Mater.* 12, 1537067. doi:10.3389/fmats.2025.1537067
- Janssen, R. H., Vincken, J.-P., Van Den Broek, L. A. M., Fogliano, V., and Lakemond, C. M. M. (2017). Nitrogen-to-Protein conversion factors for three edible insects: *Tenebrio molitor*, *Alphitobius diaperinus*, and *Hermetia illucens*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 65 (11), 2275–2278. doi:10.1021/acs.jafc.7b00471
- Jantzen Da Silva Lucas, A., Quadro Oreste, E., Leão Gouveia Costa, H., Martín López, H., Dias Medeiros Saad, C., and Prentice, C. (2021). Extraction, physicochemical characterization, and morphological properties of chitin and chitosan from cuticles of edible insects. *Food Chem.* 343, 128550. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.128550
- Karthick Rajan, D., Mohan, K., Rajarajeswaran, J., Divya, D., Kumar, R., Kandasamy, S., et al. (2024). β -Chitin and chitosan from waste shells of edible mollusks as a functional ingredient. *Food Front.* 5 (1), 46–72. doi:10.1002/fft2.326
- Khatami, N., Guerrero, P., Martín, P., Quintela, E., Ramos, V., Saa, L., et al. (2024). Valorization of biological waste from insect-based food industry: assessment of chitin and chitosan potential. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 324, 121529. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2023.121529
- Kherbache, A., Youcefi, F., Zerrouki, M., and Cherifi, A. (2022). Optimization of chitin demineralization from shrimp shells waste by response surface methodology (RSM). *South Asian J. Exp. Biol.* 12 (5), 725–734. doi:10.38150/sajeb.12(5).p725-734
- Kim, K.-M., Lee, D.-S., Nam, M.-H., Yoo, H.-S., Kim, S.-B., Chun, B.-S., et al. (2010). Optimization of alcalase for krill byproduct hydrolysis and antioxidative activities by response surface methodology. *Prev. Nutr. Food Sci.* 15 (4), 316–321. doi:10.3746/jfn.2010.15.4.316
- Kim, S. H., Choi, W., Hong, S.-J., and Kim, N.-J. (2012). Nutritional value of mealworm, *Tenebrio molitor* as food source. *Int. J. Industr. Entomol.* 25 (1), 93–98. doi:10.7852/IJIE.2012.25.1.093
- Kim, H., Kim, H., Ahn, Y., Hong, K.-B., Kim, I.-W., Choi, R.-Y., et al. (2023). The preparation and physicochemical characterization of *Tenebrio molitor* chitin using alcalase. *Molecules* 28 (7), 3254. doi:10.3390/molecules28073254
- Kozma, M., Acharya, B., and Bissessur, R. (2022). Chitin, chitosan, and Nanochitin: extraction, synthesis, and applications. *Polymers* 14 (19), 3989. doi:10.3390/polym14193989
- Kozma, M., Acharya, B., and Bissessur, R. (2024). Chemical extraction of chitin from American lobster (*Homarus americanus*) shells optimized through response surface methodology. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 256, 128462. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.128462
- Kurita, K. (2006). Chitin and chitosan: functional biopolymers from marine crustaceans. *Mar. Biotechnol.* 8 (3), 203–226. doi:10.1007/s10126-005-0097-5
- Learidi, R., Melzi, C., and Polotti, G. (s.d). CAT (Chemometric Agile Tool), freely downloadable from Available online at: <https://gruppochemiometria.it/index.php/software> [Software] (Accessed January 21, 2026).
- Luo, Q., Wang, Y., Han, Q., Ji, L., Zhang, H., Fei, Z., et al. (2019). Comparison of the physicochemical, rheological, and morphologic properties of chitosan from four insects. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 209, 266–275. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2019.01.030
- Mathew, G. M., Huang, C. C., Sindhu, R., Binod, P., Sirohi, R., Awsathi, M. K., et al. (2021). Enzymatic approaches in the bioprocessing of shellfish wastes. *3 Biotech.* 11 (8), 367. doi:10.1007/s13205-021-02912-7
- Mei, Z., Kuzhir, P., and Godeau, G. (2024). Update on chitin and chitosan from insects: sources, production, characterization, and biomedical applications. *Biomimetics* 9 (5), 297. doi:10.3390/biomimetics9050297
- Mersmann, L., Souza, V. G. L., and Fernando, A. L. (2025). Green processes for chitin and chitosan production from insects: Current state, challenges, and opportunities. *Polymers* 17 (9), 1185. doi:10.3390/polym17091185
- Milinković Budinčić, J., Radonić, Ž., Dragoljović, D., Sedlar, T., Milković, M., Polić Pasković, M., et al. (2025). Exuviae of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae as a source of chitosan: characterisation and possible applications. *Appl. Sci.* 15 (17), 9285. doi:10.3390/app15179285
- Min, B.-M., Lee, S. W., Lim, J. N., You, Y., Lee, T. S., Kang, P. H., et al. (2004). Chitin and chitosan nanofibers: electrospinning of chitin and deacetylation of chitin nanofibers. *Polymer* 45 (21), 7137–7142. doi:10.1016/j.polymer.2004.08.048
- Mohan, K., Ganesan, A. R., Ezhilarasi, P. N., Kondamareddy, K. K., Rajan, D. K., Sathishkumar, P., et al. (2022). Green and eco-friendly approaches for the extraction of chitin and chitosan: a review. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 287, 119349. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2022.119349
- Mohan Kumar, G., and Kungumapriya, R. (2025). Influence of light conditions and feed type on the growth, physiology, and nutrient composition of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae. *J. Entomol. Zool. Stud.* 13 (2), 54–57. doi:10.22271/j.ento.2025.v13.i2a.9476
- Muñoz-Seijas, N., Fernandes, H., Dominguez, J. M., and Salgado, J. M. (2025). Recent advances in biorefinery of *Tenebrio molitor* adopting green technologies. *Food Bioprocess Technol.* 18 (2), 1061–1078. doi:10.1007/s11947-024-03510-0
- Nafary, A., Mousavi Nezhad, S. A., and Jalili, S. (2023). Extraction and characterization of chitin and chitosan from *Tenebrio Molitor* beetles and investigation of its antibacterial effect against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Adv. Biomed. Res.* 12 (1), 96. doi:10.4103/abr.abr_205_22
- No, H. K., and Meyers, S. P. (1995). Preparation and characterization of chitin and chitosan—A review. *J. Aquatic Food Prod. Technol.* 4 (2), 27–52. doi:10.1300/J030v04n02_03
- Novikov, V. Yu., Derkach, S. R., Konovalova, I. N., Dolgopyatova, N. V., and Kuchina, Y. A. (2023). Mechanism of heterogeneous alkaline deacetylation of chitin: a review. *Polymers* 15 (7), 1729. doi:10.3390/polym15071729
- Pellis, A., Guebitz, G. M., and Nyamhongo, G. S. (2022). Chitosan: sources, processing and modification techniques. *Gels* 8 (7), 393. doi:10.3390/gels8070393
- Pereira, F. S., Da Silva Agostini, D. L., Job, A. E., and González, E. R. P. (2013). Thermal studies of chitin–chitosan derivatives. *J. Therm. Analysis Calorim.* 114 (1), 321–327. doi:10.1007/s10973-012-2835-z
- Pighinelli, L. (2019). Methods of chitin production a short review. *Am. J. Biomed. Sci. and Res.* 3 (4), 307–314. doi:10.34297/AJBSR.2019.03.000682
- Rehman, K. U., Hollah, C., Wiesotzki, K., Heinz, V., Aganovic, K., Rehman, R. U., et al. (2023). Insect-derived chitin and chitosan: a still unexploited resource for the edible insect sector. *Sustainability* 15 (6), 4864. doi:10.3390/su15064864
- Ribeiro, N., Abelho, M., and Costa, R. (2018). A review of the scientific literature for optimal conditions for mass rearing *Tenebrio molitor* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). *J. Entomol. Sci.* 53 (4), 434–454. doi:10.18474/JES17-67.1
- Rinaudo, M. (2006). Chitin and chitosan: properties and applications. *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 31 (7), 603–632. doi:10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2006.06.001
- Said Al Hoqani, H. A., Al-Shaqsi, N., Hossain, M. A., and Al Sibani, M. A. (2020). Isolation and optimization of the method for industrial production of chitin and chitosan from Omani shrimp shell. *Carbohydr. Res.* 492, 108001. doi:10.1016/j.carres.2020.108001
- Saravana, P. S., Ho, T. C., Chae, S.-J., Cho, Y.-J., Park, J.-S., Lee, H.-J., et al. (2018). Deep eutectic solvent-based extraction and fabrication of chitin films from crustacean waste. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 195, 622–630. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2018.05.018
- Sharma, K. M., Kumar, R., Panwar, S., and Kumar, A. (2017). Microbial alkaline proteases: optimization of production parameters and their properties. *J. Genet. Eng. Biotechnol.* 15 (1), 115–126. doi:10.1016/j.jgeb.2017.02.001
- Shetranjiwalla, S., and Ononiwu, A. (2025). Identifying barriers to scaled-up production and commercialization of chitin and chitosan using green technologies: a review and quantitative green chemistry assessment. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 305, 141062. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.141062
- Shin, C.-S., Kim, D.-Y., and Shin, W.-S. (2019). Characterization of chitosan extracted from Mealworm Beetle (*Tenebrio molitor*, Zophobas morio) and Rhinoceros Beetle (*Allomyrina dichotoma*) and their antibacterial activities. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 125, 72–77. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.11.242
- Son, Y.-J., Hwang, I.-K., Nho, C. W., Kim, S. M., and Kim, S. H. (2021). Determination of carbohydrate composition in mealworm (*Tenebrio molitor* L.) larvae and characterization of mealworm chitin and chitosan. *Foods* 10 (3), 640. doi:10.3390/foods10030640
- Sudwischer, P., Krüger, B., Sitzmann, W., and Hellwig, M. (2025). Chitin analysis in insect-based feed ingredients and mixed feed: development of a cost-effective and practical method. *J. Animal Physiol. Animal Nutr.* 109 (3), 854–866. doi:10.1111/jpn.14098
- Terkula Iber, B., Azman Kanan, N., Torsabo, D., and Wese Omuwa, J. (2022). A review of various sources of chitin and chitosan in nature. *J. Renew. Mater.* 10 (4), 1097–1123. doi:10.32604/jrm.2022.018142
- Vera Zambrano, M., Dutta, B., Mercer, D. G., MacLean, H. L., and Touchie, M. F. (2019). Assessment of moisture content measurement methods of dried food products in small-scale operations in developing countries: a review. *Trends Food Sci. and Technol.* 88, 484–496. doi:10.1016/j.tifs.2019.04.006
- Verardi, A., Sangiorgio, P., Moliterni, S., Errico, S., Spagnoletta, A., and Dimatteo, S. (2023). Advanced technologies for chitin recovery from crustacean waste. *Clean Technol. Recycl.* 3 (1), 4–43. doi:10.3934/ctr.2023002
- Weißpflog, J., Vehlou, D., Müller, M., Kohn, B., Scheler, U., Boye, S., et al. (2021). Characterization of chitosan with different degree of deacetylation and equal viscosity in dissolved and solid state – insights by various complementary methods. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 171, 242–261. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2021.01.010
- Younes, I., and Rinaudo, M. (2015). Chitin and chitosan preparation from marine sources. Structure, properties and applications. *Mar. Drugs* 13 (3), 1133–1174. doi:10.3390/md13031133
- Zainol Abidin, N. A., Kormin, F., Zainol Abidin, N. A., Mohamed Anuar, N. A. F., and Abu Bakar, M. F. (2020). The potential of insects as alternative sources of chitin: an overview on the chemical method of extraction from various sources. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 21 (14), 4978. doi:10.3390/ijms21144978
- Zarzosa, G. I. G., and Kobayashi, T. (2025). Regenerated chitin from insect sources and fabrication of their hydrogel films as an alternative from marine sources. *Biomass Convers. Biorefinery* 15 (7), 9835–9848. doi:10.1007/s13399-024-05686-z
- Zawadzki, J., and Kaczmarek, H. (2010). Thermal treatment of chitosan in various conditions. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 80 (2), 394–400. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2009.11.037